

Технология непрерывного сопровождения тьютором профессионального самоопределения обучающихся

В. А. ДАВЫДЕНКО, С. В. ЧЕБРОВСКАЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Введение. Для сохранения конкурентоспособности на рынке труда, адаптации к быстрым изменениям и для личностного роста граждан, международным сообществом утверждена концепция постоянного приобретения новых знаний и развития навыков, не ограничиваясь рамками формального образования. Функции педагогов, сохраняя роль организационной деятельности, расширяются от традиционного обучения и воспитания к новым ролям консультанта, наставника, тьютора. Утверждаются новые педагогические позиции, направленные, в том числе, на помощь обучающимся в быстро меняющемся производственном мире.

Цель исследования: разработка технологии непрерывного сопровождения тьютором профессионального самоопределения обучающихся в уровнях общего образования.

Материалы и методы. Материалом исследования послужили источники, раскрывающие нормативно-правовую основу и существующую практику профориентирующей работы. Использованы статьи авторитетных изданий периодической печати, материалы научных конференций. Применены методы анализа литературы и моделирование.

Результаты. Описана технология тьюторского сопровождения, представляющая собой комплекс компонентов, системно применяемых для достижения predetermined результатов в профессиональном самоопределении обучающихся. Разработаны модель деятельности тьютора, сопровождающего профессиональное самоопределение обучающихся в образовательном процессе учреждений общего образования от дошкольного до среднего общего, с перспективой продления в учреждениях профессионального образования, а также алгоритм тьюторской работы, реализуемый на каждом из общеобразовательных уровней.

Заключение. Предлагаемая технология способна внести вклад в реализацию задач индивидуализации обучения в учреждениях общего образования. А также содействовать культивированию таких личностных качеств как самостоятельность и ответственность у молодых людей, входящих в мир профессионального труда.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

профессиональное самоопределение, непрерывное сопровождение, индивидуализация, тьютор

Для цитирования: Давыденко В. А., Чебровская С. В. Технология непрерывного сопровождения тьютором профессионального самоопределения обучающихся // Перспективы науки и образования. 2025. № 5. С. 56–68. <https://doi.org/10.32744/pse.2025.5.4>

Поступила: 15.04.2024 | Одобрена: 12.06.2025 | Опубликована: 31.10.2025

Лицензия «С указанием авторства — С сохранением условий». Позволяет перерабатывать, исправлять и развивать произведения при условии указания авторства и лицензирования производных работ на аналогичных условиях.

Technology of Continuous Tutor Support for Students' Professional Self-Determination

V. A. DAVYDENKO, S. V. CHEBROVSKAYA

ABSTRACT

Introduction. To maintain competitiveness in the labor market, adapt to rapid changes, and foster personal growth, the international community has endorsed the concept of lifelong learning, emphasizing continuous acquisition of new knowledge and skills beyond the limits of formal education. While retaining their organizational functions, educators' roles are expanding from traditional teaching and upbringing toward new functions as consultants, mentors, and tutors. New pedagogical positions are being established, including assisting students in navigating a rapidly changing professional environment.

Research Objective: To develop a technology for continuous tutor support of students' professional self-determination across general education levels.

Materials and Methods. The study draws on sources outlining the legal and regulatory framework and current practices in career guidance. Articles from reputable periodicals and conference materials were used. Literature analysis and modeling methods were applied.

Results. The study describes a tutor support technology, consisting of an integrated set of components systematically applied to achieve predetermined outcomes in students' professional self-determination. A model of tutor activity is developed, supporting students' professional self-determination throughout the educational process in general education (preschool through secondary) with potential extension to vocational education institutions. An algorithm of tutor work is also proposed, to be implemented at each general education level.

Conclusion. The proposed technology can contribute to the implementation of individualized learning in general education institutions and promote the development of personal qualities such as independence and responsibility in young people entering the professional workforce.

KEYWORDS

professional self-determination, continuous support, individualization, tutor

For Citation: Davydenko, V. A., & Chebrovskaya, S. V. (2025). Technology of Continuous Tutor Support for Students' Professional Self-Determination. *Perspektivy nauki i obrazovaniya = Perspectives of Science and Education*, (5), 56–68. <https://doi.org/10.32744/pse.2025.5.4>

Received: 15 April 2025 | Approved: 12 June 2025 | Published: 31 October 2025

This is an open access article distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike International License (CC-BY-SA 4.0) that allows others to share the work with an acknowledgement of the work's authorship and initial publication in this journal

INTRODUCTION

The United Nations General Assembly's global plan to ensure that every citizen has the right to a prosperous future envisions that all member states strive to achieve the goals set forth in the Sustainable Development Agenda. There are seventeen such goals. According to the fourth goal (SDG 4), "Quality Education for All Throughout Life", every citizen should have the opportunity to acquire competitiveness in some field of employment through the development of vocational and technical skills [1]. The importance of achieving this goal is confirmed by the direct influence of education on the implementation of subsequent Sustainable Development Goals. For example, it contributes to economic well-being, financial growth, and access to decent work (SDG 8), reduces inequality within countries (SDG 10), and strengthens mechanisms for activating work at various levels of partnerships aiming to meet people's needs (SDG 17) [2].

Prosperity, employability, and a sustainable future require that each citizen master a profession, a process that unfolds throughout life through education at all levels. However, quality education is impossible without pedagogical support. This support must come not only from subject teachers (whose primary function is to prepare students to master the curriculum, or at minimum, the fundamentals of a given branch of knowledge) but also from specialists in related fields: social educators, educational psychologists, career guidance experts, and other social service professionals [3]. Such support is viewed not as a one-off situational intervention, but as continuous assistance built on the principles of inter-level continuity, individualized learning, and recognition of the individual moving toward their professional future [4]. In other words, there arises the need to develop a targeted, long-term, and structured system of support for students' professional self-determination provided by a specialist trained specifically for this purpose – certain technology.

Experience in applying such technologies exists in international educational practice. For instance, the need to maintain strict sequencing (technology) in learning – from topic assessments to learning outcomes – is discussed in the study by J. Chevalère and colleagues [5]. The use of technology to support students' educational needs in institutions is demonstrated in a collective study by A. Mohammed and associates [6]. Step-by-step guidance in decision-making by older adults is described in the work of H.S. Lee, R.A. Mudar, and W.A. Rogers [7]. A review of assistive technologies supporting children with neurodevelopmental disorders is presented in a joint publication by scholars from Italy, the USA, Australia, and Singapore [8]. The role of technology as a targeted career intervention program for preparing high school students for career choice is explored in the work of T. Babarovic and colleagues [9].

International practice also offers examples of implementing educational technologies with the involvement of various social service specialists (social agents): tutors, mentors, school counselors, and others. Examples include assisting students in mastering courses through collaborative learning [10], peer tutoring [11], online tutoring [12], and peer mentorship in schools [13] and extracurricular institutions [14]. P. Irwin and colleagues demonstrate the impact of embedded support from educational staff on the adaptation of newly enrolled students [15]. K.J. Topping proposes a model of intergenerational mentoring [16]. Multiple research teams have studied the role of school counselors in developing students' academic success [17].

Particular attention is given to the continuity of support for youth in their professional development. For example, M.T. Molekoa and colleagues describe the duration-specific aspects of career guidance provided by teachers in full-cycle schools [18]. The involvement of practitioners and vocational training masters in school career guidance activities is discussed in the article by S.O. Chukwuedo, I.M. Onwusuru, and N.M. Agbo [19]. The impact of school specialists with diverse profiles on the effectiveness of students' career orientation is examined in the study by L. Hearne and S. Neary [20].

Proposals have been made in favor of early career guidance for preschool children [21] and integrating compulsory school education with simultaneous immersion in professional experience [22]. It is suggested to establish continuity between educational institutions and employers, involving collaboration among school teachers, vocational educators, and industry representatives [23], as well as developing a comprehensive system of career guidance services at least at the regional level [24].

The Russian Federation is an active supporter of UN initiatives in the field of education. In accordance with the Presidential Decree *On National Development Goals of the Russian Federation until 2030 and prospects through 2036*, as well as national projects *Youth and Children and Personnel*, and through initiatives such as *Professional Training, Leading Schools, and Education for the Labor Market*, the Russian education system aims to create comprehensive conditions for students' professional self-determination at all stages up to employment. A priority in this direction is ensuring equal opportunities for children with disabilities and special educational needs (including gifted children). All career guidance activities are aimed at enabling students to make timely and informed choices regarding professions that will allow them to succeed in modern socio-economic conditions and be in demand at the municipal, regional, and national levels.

By 2030, a key task is the formation and maintenance of an effective national system designed for the comprehensive identification, support, and development of each student's talents. This system is intended to facilitate personal self-determination, conscious career choice, and professional self-realization. In implementation of the Presidential Decree, educational institutions are already conducting measures such as early career guidance in kindergartens and primary schools, and introducing a unified career guidance model (the so-called professional minimum) for middle school students. Special attention is paid to the involvement of students with disabilities in all forms of these activities using an inclusive approach. Key projects in this area include the Abilympics championship [25].

At the same time, according to the Interdepartmental Working Group of the Government of the Russian Federation for responding to the labor market situation, over 1.6 million people graduated from universities and colleges in 2024. Approximately 823,000 students completed bachelor's, specialist, and master's programs, of whom 68% of bachelor's and specialist program graduates, and 84% of master's program graduates, were employed. Around 860,000 students completed secondary vocational education programs, with 66% employed. These figures include those registered as self-employed or individual entrepreneurs [26].

Khabarovsk Krai is among the regions with the highest proportion of employed graduates from secondary vocational education institutions (58%). At the same time, data from Khabarovsk Krai indicate that many graduates encounter difficulties in finding employment within the first year after obtaining their qualifications. For example, according to the regional employment and labor placement center, in 2023 and 2024, 104 and 81 secondary vocational education (SVE) graduates, respectively, sought assistance from the center immediately after graduation. From higher education institutions, 29 and 18 graduates, respectively, required support. This trend is particularly pronounced among youth with disabilities [27]. During 2021–2022, 298 young people with disabilities completed programs at the region's SVE institutions. By autumn 2023, 225 of them (54.6% of all young specialists seeking assistance from the employment service) already required support in job search. The types of assistance most in demand were: career guidance activities provided to 136 individuals (60.4%); psychological support received by 36 young people (16%); and social adaptation services in the labor market utilized by 34 individuals (15.1%) [28].

Contemporary research on students' readiness for professional self-determination highlights a complex of systemic issues. These include insufficient cooperation among supporting specialists, disruption in the continuity of educational stages regarding career path development, low parental involvement, and the formal approach of teachers in implementing career guidance "minimum" programs. A significant obstacle is the lack of targeted training for teachers in career guidance activities and their limited time resources, which is especially acute when working with students with special educational needs [29].

Analysis shows that, despite long-term systematic work on career guidance in schools, graduates' professional trajectories remain insufficiently effective. Traditional forms of this activity demonstrate limited results, indicating the need for new approaches to preparing students for successful professional life. The study aimed to develop a technology for continuous support of students' professional self-determination by a purposefully trained specialist – a tutor.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials for this study primarily included the legal and regulatory framework governing career guidance activities in the general education system, as well as a synthesis of Russian and international experience in assisting students with professional pathway selection. The theoretical basis of the study consisted of normative documents, including the UN Sustainable Development Agenda, the Presidential Decree of the Russian Federation *On National Development Goals of the Russian Federation*, Federal State Educational Standards (FSSES) for general education, and methodological recommendations on career guidance minimum programs. Scientific sources included publications in reputable domestic and international journals (*Herald of Volgograd State Pedagogical University*, *Bulletin of Perm State Humanitarian and Pedagogical University*, *Education and Information Technologies*, *International Journal of Educational and Career Guidance*), conference materials, and systematic reviews.

RESULTS

Analysis of the materials allowed the identification and synthesis of the specifics of the pedagogical staff’s work in implementing career guidance programs. This pedagogical activity is regulated by Federal State Educational Standards (FSSES), implemented within the framework of main educational programs (MEP) and upbringing programs, and coordinated according to the Unified Career Guidance Model (UCGM).

The collected information formed the basis for developing a sequence of assistance to students in constructing a personal trajectory toward their professional future by a teacher adopting a new professional role – a tutor. In other words, this constitutes a tutor-based technology for supporting students’ professional self-determination at the preschool, primary, basic, and secondary general education levels. A generalized model of tutor activity integrated into the educational process of institutions is illustrated in Figure 1 (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Model of Tutor Activity in General Education Institutions for Supporting Students’ Professional Self-Determination

Figure translation:

top line: Pre-professional period; Proto-fessional preparatory period; Professional period

second line: FAMILY UPBRINGING; FORMATION OF KNOWLEDGE/SKILLS IN LEARNERS BY EDUCATORS, SUBJECT TEACHERS IN ACCORDANCE WITH THE MAIN EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM

ovals: family environment 0-3 years; preschool education 3-7 years; primary general education 7-11 years; basic general education 11-16 years; secondary general education 17-18 years; secondary vocational education 19-...; higher education 19-...

columns: basic psychological, cognitive, social, and personal introductions to work and self-care; appearance of a work image; formation of a professional community; verification of the image of a suitable variant for a professional destiny and choice of an educational institution; approbation of the specialization image

last line: MENTORING BY A TUTOR FOR THE PROFESSIONAL SELF-DETERMINATION OF STUDENTS

As illustrated in the figure, student professionalization can be divided into three periods: pre-professional, proto-professional, and professional. Purposeful tutor support for students' professional self-determination, as subjects of professional labor, begins in kindergarten, continues through school, and gradually transitions to obtaining a profession in secondary vocational education institutions and universities. The latter stage remains a topic for future exploration. Below, we outline the main principles of tutor activity according to the stated research objective.

Following the approach of G.K. Selevko, the support technology is conceived as a designed system that integrates all components of the pedagogical process. Organized within a temporal and spatial continuum, this system aims to achieve predetermined outcomes. Its key components include the participants in educational relationships and the organizations delivering educational activities. The former group comprises students, their parents/legal guardians, and educational staff (subject teachers, educational psychologists, speech therapists, social educators, and specialists working with various categories of students). The latter group includes educational institutions and research organizations, social service providers, and other social agents (individual entrepreneurs, vocational training masters, enterprise representatives).

Like any pedagogical process, tutor work is structured around several core components: mission, goals, objectives, principles, as well as forms, methods, tools, and outcomes. In the context of tutoring, each component has its specific characteristics.

The mission of tutor support for students' professional self-determination is to fulfill FSES requirements by ensuring that every student (including those with disabilities and gifted students) as the opportunity for conscious professional path selection.

The goal of tutoring is to promote the development of students' capacities for independent acquisition of new knowledge and skills, self-development, and self-improvement through active engagement with new social experiences.

The objectives of tutoring are twofold: first, to organize an educational environment that enables students of all categories to pursue individualized educational pathways/projects according to their personal needs, abilities, interests, and characteristics; second, to provide organizational and methodological support for the implementation of these individualized pathways and projects.

The principles of support include: inter-level continuity, ensuring sequential and cyclical progression of support at each stage of student development; individualized learning, implemented through clear goal orientation, systematization, variability, and flexibility of methods; and comprehensive consideration of students' individual and personal characteristics, emphasizing advisory rather than directive guidance from specialists.

Tutor support is implemented using a variety of forms. These primarily include group formats: scenario-based role-playing and didactic games, educational seminars (tutorials) including sessions for parents, as well as educational events, workshops, webinars, and excursions. The tutor's key instruments remain individual consultations conducted on request. Their classification depends on the task, stage, and goal of interaction. Consultations may be introductory, thematic, working, analytical, or final.

Tools and resources for tutor support include primarily scenario-based role-playing and didactic games, mapping, portfolio compilation, and the tutor's diary. Career guidance resources include exhibitions, excursions, presentations, open days, and more. Career information tools encompass reference literature, informational materials, educational films, etc. Career adaptation resources include professional trials, masterclasses, and training sessions.

Methods of support include a combination of psychopedagogical diagnostics, organization of practice-oriented activities, and active and interactive learning techniques. Applied methods comprise case studies (analyzing existing and creating new practical situations), project-based approaches (e.g., portfolio creation and optimization of personal life space), debates, analytical techniques, self-reflection, and elements of independent work. A central strategy in tutoring is targeted work with questions, whose content evolves according to the stage of professional development. In the pre-professional period, the focus is on fostering cognitive activity. In the proto-professional period, questions primarily aim at refining and developing the "self-project", designing and analyzing the individual development trajectory, planning the route, and implementing it via an individualized program as an indicator of conscious self-determination.

The ultimate outcome of tutoring is the formation of a student's authorial approach to career planning and an individual vision of their professional future. A graduate of tutor-supported guidance becomes an agent of their own choices: they independently manage their career self-determination process, set goals, make conscious and responsible decisions, locate and critically evaluate information, and organize an effective system for work and personal space. Intermediate outcomes (results at each educational level or age stage) are presented in our other publications.

The typical algorithm of tutor activity includes the following:

- Establish contact with the tutee (and their parents/legal guardians, if necessary);
- Receive the request for support;
- Determine the tutee's individual route to achieving their goal based on the request;
- Build the tutee's individual development trajectory;
- Develop an individualized educational program to address shortfalls and achieve the tutee's goal;
- Implement educational events;
- Analyze results.

The tutor's algorithm remains fundamentally the same across all educational levels, with minor adaptations depending on the tutee's age or category (giftedness, disabilities, etc.). In other words, tutor support is cyclical – the same action algorithm applies at each educational stage. The algorithm is conveniently illustrated in Figure 2 (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2 Algorithm of Tutor Activities in Supporting the Professional Self-Determination of the Tutee

Figure translation:

K – C; 3 – R; ИОМ – ИЕМ (mapping); ИОТ – ИЕТ (history, diagnostics); ИОП – ИЕП (social agents); ОО – ЕЕ (educational environment); А – А (portfolio)

As the figure shows, the tutor's activity begins with establishing contact (C). At the initial stage of guidance, it is crucial to create a positive atmosphere and psychological comfort for the tutee. This helps establish productive interaction and fosters readiness for further cooperation. Thus, the tutor's first task is to develop and sustain the tutee's motivation for self-directed learning.

The next step is receiving a request (R) – clarifying information regarding the tutee's expressed interest. The main tool at this stage is personal resource mapping, which makes it possible to assemble and structure the tutee's individual resource profile. The distinctive features of such map include: symbols to represent various objects; orientation, showing the direction and distance of objects relative to the center or to one another; and a scale, indicating the degree of reduction of objects while preserving proportionality. Thanks to these properties, the map enables the tutee to view themselves and their actions in a new context, to evaluate the partiality of their actions in relation to the whole, and to understand the specifics of their own activity within a broader system.

Once all intermediate points and goals on the path have been identified, the next stage is diagnosing the tutee's learning gaps, leading to the construction of an Individual Educational Trajectory (IET). The main tools here are anamnesis and diagnostic assessments carried out by the tutor. Examining the tutee's life history, consulting characteristics from related specialists, analyzing performance in academic subjects, as well as evaluating the development of key structural components of professional self-determination (motivational, foundational, operational, and communicative), makes it possible to design an Individual Educational Program (IEP) that accounts for all conditions necessary to fulfill the request.

The tutee then proceeds to independently implement the IEP through participation in all planned activities, that is, through educational events (EE). In this interpretation, an educational event is a pedagogical tool initiated by the tutor. Its purpose is to objectify the process by which the tutee designs their professional pathway, and to transform this process into educational content. The impact of such events is twofold. On the one hand, the tutee acquires competencies for productive, independent action. On the other, the tutor gains the opportunity to move learning beyond formal procedures toward achieving personalized and meaningful educational outcomes. A particular function of the tutor at this stage is, as needed, to arrange interaction and communication between the tutee and social agents or beneficiaries.

The cycle concludes with analysis/reflection (A) on the completed pathway, aiming to obtain feedback on the results achieved and to make any necessary adjustments. At this stage, the feasibility of continuing the search for information along the given parameters (request and route) is assessed, or a rationale for shifting to a new search strategy is provided.

In cases where comprehensive support by a single tutor is difficult to organize within one educational institution (for example, if different tutors work at each educational level), the tutor's activity at the next level begins once again with establishing contact (C). Ideally, however, one tutor would accompany the tutee (as a future subject of professional activity) across all periods: pre-professional, pre-vocational, and vocational. In this context, maintaining a tutor's diary and a universal portfolio by the tutee becomes especially important.

Thus, tutor support represents a comprehensive process covering the entire path of forming an individualized educational program: from identifying and developing a child's cognitive interests in preschool, through research and project activities, to providing consultative support in choosing and mastering professional education programs.

A mandatory condition of this technology is maintaining personal portfolios by both the tutor and, whenever possible, the tutee. Ideally, the portfolio is updated at the completion of each action in the cycle, regardless of the educational level. The tutor may keep a portfolio over several years, recording reflections on the tutee, the tools and methods applied, and their effectiveness. The

tutee (with the exception of preschoolers and the earliest primary grades) accumulates material by tracking the key points of their educational trajectory, structuring and modifying it over time.

The limited format of this article does not allow for a detailed presentation of the specifics of tutor support at each level of education; these materials will be presented in future publications.

DISCUSSION

The research findings were presented at the international scientific-practical conference Supporting Personal Self-Development in the Context of the Family and Educational Organization, within the section From Self-Determination to Self-Development: The Trajectory of Continuous Professionalization, held in October 2024 at Pacific State University (Khabarovsk). Participants in the section agreed on a common understanding of professional self-determination as a process in which the individual, acting as an active subject, makes a series of choices that define their professional stance and, consequently, their trajectory. This process unfolds in dialectical interaction with the objective reality of the external world and the social environment. Within this framework, special emphasis was placed on the role of reflection in enabling the subject to become aware of themselves, their past experiences, the present moment, and their vision of the future. These conclusions are consistent with the findings of international scholars V. Duprez, L. Haerens, A.V. Hecke [30] and S. Odem, K. Kellett, K. Whalen [31].

In this context, tutor support is understood as a specialist's activity in creating the conditions under which the tutee is able to make an independent and optimal decision about their professional future. The aim of such support is to help the learner recognize their personal role in career choice and construction, while also teaching them to independently plan and carry out steps toward the chosen profession. The central principle is that responsibility for the choice lies with the tutee; the specialist merely enables them to assume that responsibility. This approach aligns with the position of T.M. Kovaleva and her research team, who provided the theoretical foundation for tutoring within the education system as a whole [32]. Tutoring here is structured according to the principles of open education in an anthropological context. The core idea is to create an environment that consolidates all the resources necessary for the learner's individual educational route, enabling them to form a conscious request regarding the content and format of their education, to define personal educational goals and priorities, to design methods of self-learning, and ultimately to develop an individual educational program, thereby independently constructing their experience of self-formation.

Distinctive features of tutor support for professional self-determination include situations of choice uncertainty and an abundant environment. Situations of uncertainty are treated as a necessary resource: a space of possibilities in which personal interest emerges. Interaction is based not on rigid external prescriptions but on agreements and norms co-developed by the tutor and the tutee. An abundant environment, meanwhile, is a deliberately constructed space (informational, social, cultural) in which the number of opportunities consciously exceeds necessity, thus ensuring the learner has genuine options. The key result of such work is the "advancement" of interest – from the passive stance of "I am interested" toward active engagement: carrying out an educational project, shaping one's own trajectory, and adopting a reflective professional stance.

At the same time, our study showed that, unlike the framework presented by other authors [33], the tutor organizes the tutee's work according to the vector "present-future-past-future". The "present-future" segment is structured at the moment the request is received. The "past" is considered in terms of the individual educational trajectory (IET) – the traces of the subject's earlier path of professionalization. The tutor's work with the IET involves joint reflection with the tutee on prior educational steps, accumulated "career practice" (realized trials and projects), and identified deficits, with subsequent re-evaluation in the context of the present state, plans, and intentions forming the basis of the request. The tutor's efforts are directed toward supporting the learner in choosing means that foster the development of mental functions necessary for understanding their own resources and for formulating possible versions of their educational future. It is at this stage that the design of the individual educational program (IEP) also begins. Work on the IEP corresponds to the "future" segment of the vector: the tutor creates conditions and mobilizes specific resources to help the tutee become aware of their goals, clarify their intentions, and build further educational steps through analysis of images and trends of the future. These findings correspond to those of

other scholars [34], who stress the critical importance of event formats, that is, educational events that allow the tutee to “discover themselves” in the horizons of the future.

Regarding the technologization of professional self-determination support, our results resonate with the findings of T.S. Dorokhova [35] and L.R. Salavatulina [36], along with their respective research groups, in working with both delinquent adolescents and academically successful students in specialized classes. However, our results did not confirm those of studies focused on supporting students with disabilities [37], specifically in terms of the sequence of forming the structural components of professional self-determination. For neurotypical learners, interests and motivation for future professional activity emerge first, followed by reflection on psychophysical attributes relative to the requirements of the chosen profession, and then work on strengthening or developing those attributes. For learners with disabilities, by contrast, the effectiveness of professional self-determination depends primarily on their awareness of their own psychophysical resources and their capacity to work with them. Nevertheless, the observed divergences do not contradict the overall technology of support: all components of the technology and the algorithm of actions are upheld, and the methods and instruments have proven both in demand and effective.

As for tutoring technologies across different educational levels, our findings are consistent with those of prior research involving preschool children [38], primary school pupils [39], adolescents [40], and high school students [41]. We share the view of these authors on the value of early career guidance, the dependence of professionalization quality on conditions for developing learner agency, and the importance of continuity of tutor support across levels of education.

The algorithm for tutor support in professional self-determination confirms the stages described in theory [42]. Establishing contact and formulating the request correspond to the first, orientation-diagnostic stage of support theory. At this stage, the tutor and the learner (tutee) become acquainted. The tutee explains how their interest in a subject first arose. The tutor’s task is to understand the learner’s educational goals, interests, aptitudes, and plans for the future, taking into account their age.

The development of an individual educational trajectory and program corresponds to the design stage. At this point, the tutee compiles a thematic portfolio that includes: a historical overview of the chosen topic, their previous work, a list of useful resources, a plan of further actions, and an inventory of the necessary equipment. The tutor’s task here is to provide consultations, help formulate questions, and support the tutee’s independence in finding a unique approach to studying the selected topic.

Participation in educational events marks the implementation stage. At this stage, a real project is carried out, a presentation portfolio is assembled, and the obtained results are presented.

The final stage, the analytical stage, is self-explanatory. Its key element is the organization of reflection (individual or collective), intended to provide each tutee with detailed feedback from the tutor. The process concludes with planning for future activities: recording preferences regarding subject matter and material format (individual or group), as well as defining the personal role of each participant in the next phase of work.

CONCLUSION

Thus, tutor-supported guidance for students’ professional self-determination as a technology is purposeful, feasible, in demand, and holds potential for implementation within the general education system. At present, such guidance develops at each individual level of education, which does not fully realize its potential. Centralized support from educational authorities is required. A promising area for further research is the study of continuity in tutor guidance across general and vocational education institutions.

This approach will provide the educational community with the opportunity to address the challenges of individualization across all age levels. Comprehensive tutor-supported guidance for professional self-determination will cultivate independence and responsibility in each student, develop skills in decision-making and resource utilization for constructing a personal educational path toward

their professional future, and foster the internal readiness to consciously plan, adjust, and implement their personal development.

FUNDING

This research was supported by the Russian Science Foundation grant No. 24-28-20226 (<https://rscf.ru/project/24-28-20226/>) and the Ministry of Education and Science of Khabarovsk Krai (Agreement No. 117C/2024).

REFERENCES

1. United Nations Charter (full text). 2015. Available at: <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/un-charter/full-text> (accessed 30.09.2024).
2. 4th global report on adult learning and education: leave no one behind: participation, equity and inclusion. 2020. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000372274> (accessed 30.09.2024).
3. Davidenko, V. A. The Tutor as a Personal Coach for Achieving Learners' Individually-Oriented Goals. *Herald of Volgograd State Pedagogical University*, 2025, no. 1(194), pp. 52-58.
4. Chebrovskaya, S. V. The Issue of Teacher Competence in Supporting Students' Professional Self-Determination. *Herald of Volgograd State Pedagogical University*, 2025, no. 1(194), pp. 71-79.
5. Cheval`ere J., Yun H. S., Henke A., Pinkwart N., Hafner V., Lazarides R. A sequence of learning processes in an intelligent tutoring system from topic-related appraisals to learning gains. *Learning and Instruction*, 2023. no. 87. Available at: https://www.dfki.de/fileadmin/user_upload/import/14687_1-s2.0-S0959475223000683-main.pdf (accessed 15.06.2025).
6. Mohammed A., Amoah Ch., Abdulai I. Technology integration on infrastructure to support educational needs in a college in Ghana. *Infrastructure Asset Management*, 2025. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/org/science/article/abs/pii/S205302502500017X> (accessed 29.06.2025).
7. Lee H.S., Mudar R.A., Rogers W.A. Understanding Medicare-related decision-making by older adults: Role of technology support. *Human Factors in Healthcare*, 2025, vol. 7. Available at: https://academic.oup.com/innovateage/article/8/Supplement_1/472/7936686 (accessed 19.06.2025).
8. Shahini A., Kamath A.P., Sharma E., Salvi M., Tan R.-S., Siuly S., Seoni S., Ganguly R., Devi A., Deo R., Barua P.D., Acharya U.R. A systematic review for artificial intelligence-driven assistive technologies to support children with neurodevelopmental disorders. *Information Fusion*, 2025, vol. 124. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1566253525005147> (accessed 19.06.2025).
9. Babarovic T., Devic I., Blazev M. The effects of middle-school career intervention on students' career readiness. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance*, 2020, vol. 20(2), pp. 429-450. doi: 10.1007/s10775-019-09411-5
10. Li Y. et al. Peer tutoring models in collaborative learning of mathematical problem solving and their effect on group achievement. *Education and Information Technologies*, 2023, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 6595-6618. doi: 10.1007/s10639-022-11429-2
11. Longjohn, Osila K. Effect of peer tutoring on senior secondary school students' academic performance in mathematics in ahoada east local government area of Rivers State. *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 2022, no. 7(4), pp. 164-169. doi: 10.36348/sjhss.2022.v07i04.008
12. Menshikova M., Bonaccia I., Scarozza D. Rethinking Tutoring Activities in the New Normal: New Ways of Tutoring and Evolution of the Tutor's Profile. *Procedia Computer Science: 6th International Conference on Industry 4.0 and Smart Manufacturing*, 2025, vol. 253. pp. 1515-1524.
13. Thurston A., Cockerill M., Chiang T. Assessing the Differential Effects of Peer Tutoring for Tutors and Tutees. *Education Sciences*, 2021, no. 11(3), pp. 97. doi: 10.3390/educsci11030097
14. Topping K.J. The effectiveness of peer tutoring in further and higher education: A typology and review of the literature. *Higher Education*, 1996, vol. 32, pp. 321-345. doi: 10.1007/BF00138870
15. Irwin P., Magee D., Weiley Sh., Teakel S., Linden K. Improving student success and retention in first-year nursing through embedded tutor support. *Nurse Education Today*, 2024, vol. 136. Available at: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0260691724000443> (accessed 19.04.2025).
16. Topping K.J. A theoretical model of intergenerational tutoring. *Journal of Intergenerational Relationships*, 2020, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 88-105. doi: 10.1080/15350770.2019.1646182
17. Hamelin G., Viviers S., Litalien D., Boulet J. Bringing light to school counselors' burnout. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational*, 2023, vol. 23(3), pp. 741-761. doi: 10.1007/s10775-022-09534-2
18. Molekoa M.T., Ubisi L., Sefotho M., Ferreira R. Full-service schoolteachers' views of career construction for tutees with visual impairment. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance*, 2023, vol. 23(2), pp. 421-440. doi: 10.1007/s10775-022-09534-2

19. Chukwuedo S.O., Onwusuru I.M., Agbo N.M. Practitioners' vocational guidance with direct learning model: influencing career commitment and employability in electrical/electronic technology education. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance*, 2022, vol. 22(1), pp. 23-48. doi: 10.1007/s10775-021-09471-6
20. Hearne L., Neary S. Let's talk about career guidance in secondary schools! A consideration of the professional capital of school staff in Ireland and England. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance*, 2021, vol. 21(1), pp. 1-14. doi: 10.1007/s10775-020-09424-5.
21. Habayib H., Cinamon R.G. Preschool teachers' attitudes toward career education: the role of cultural context and teaching self-efficacy. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance*, 2023, vol. 23(2), pp. 399-419. doi: 10.1007/s10775-021-09519-7
22. Martensson A. Creating continuity between school and workplace: VET teachers' in-school work to overcome boundaries. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 2022, vol. 74(4), pp. 682-700. doi: 10.1080/13636820.2020.1829009
23. Luthi F., Stalder B.E., Elfering A. Apprentices' resources at work and school in Switzerland: A person-centred approach. *International Journal for Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 2021, vol. 8(2), pp. 224-250. doi: 10.13152/IJRVET.8.2.5
24. Hlouskova L., Sprlak T. Career/lifelong guidance systems and services: continuous transformations in a transition region: The case of three Central and Eastern European Countries Borbely-Pecze. *International Journal for Educational and Vocational Guidance*, 2022, vol. 22(1), pp. 67-91. doi: 10.1007/s10775-021-09471-6
25. Chebrovskaya, S. V., & Chebrovskiy, A. A. Pedagogical Support as a Condition for Timely Professional Self-Determination of Students. *Modern Problems of Science and Education*, 2022, no. 4. Available at: <https://science-education.ru/article/view?id=31923> (accessed: 20.01.2025). doi: 10.17513/spno.31923
26. Golikova, T. This Year, Universities and Colleges Graduated Over 1.6 Million Young Specialists. Available at: <http://government.ru/news/53224/> (accessed 13.08.2025).
27. Professional Education in Khabarovsk Krai. Available at: <https://minobr.khabkrai.ru/Deyatelnost/Professionalnoe-obrazovanie/330/> (accessed 02.08.2025)
28. Employment Support Measures for Persons with Disabilities. Interactive Portal of the Committee on Labor and Employment of the Population of Khabarovsk Krai. Available at: <https://sz27.ru/content/> (accessed: 26.12.2024).
29. Experts Discussed the Problem of Youth Career Guidance at the IV All-Russian Forum of Students and Secondary Vocational Education Specialists "Team Profi". Available at: <https://rosatom-academy.ru/media/novosti/eksperty-obsudili-problemu-proforientatsii-molodezhi-na-iv-vserossiyskom-forume-studentov-i-spetsial/> (accessed: 06.08.2025).
30. Duprez V., Haerens L., Hecke A.V. Self-Determination Theory to observe healthcare professionals' counselling in chronic care encounters: Development of the COUNSEL-CCE tool. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 2021, vol. 104 (7). pp. 1773-1780. doi: 10.1016/j.pec.2020.12.002
31. Odem S., Kellett K., Whalen K. Best Practices for Self-Awareness and Professionalism to Meet the Curriculum Outcomes and Entrustable Professional Activities. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 2025, vol. 89(5). doi: 10.1016/j.ajpe.2025.101404.
32. Kovaleva, T. M., & Yakubovskaya, T. V. Tutoring as Anthropopractice: Between Individual Educational Trajectory and Individual Educational Program. Available at: <https://nsuem.ru/scientific-activities/publishing-nsuem/chelovek-ru/n12/pdf/> (accessed 15.08.2025).
33. Kovaleva, T. M., Terov, A. A., Khachatryan, E. V., Gracheva, N. Yu., Dudchik, S. V., & Karastelev, V. E. Tutoring in Contemporary Education: From Theory to Practice. Monograph. Moscow, Moscow City Pedagogical University, 2023. 212 p.
34. Kosykh, N. A. Pedagogical Conditions for Designing Individual Educational Trajectories of Adolescents in Temporary Child Collectives. Author's abstract for Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences degree. Moscow, 2024. 26 p.
35. Dorokhova, T. S., & Dorokhova, E. S. Tutoring Support of Professional Self-Determination of Delinquent Adolescents in the Context of A. S. Makarenko's Legacy. In: *A. S. Makarenko's Educational System as a Basis for Organizing Collective Productive Labor and Productive Activities of Children and Adolescents: Materials of the International Scientific and Practical Conference*. Moscow, 2022, pp. 53-59.
36. Salavatulina, L. R., Vorozheykina, A. V., & Khalaimova, K. A. Tutoring Support of Students in Specialized Classes as a Tool for Individualization of Pre-Professional Pedagogical Education. *Pedagogical Research Review*, 2022, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 64-68.
37. Egorova, P. A., & Chernyavskaya, A. P. Tutoring Support for Professional Self-Determination of Children with Disabilities and Children with Special Needs in Distance Learning. In: *Fundamental Achievements and Progressive Views in Education: Materials of the II International Scientific and Practical Conference Dedicated to the 20th Anniversary of the Department of Practical and Special Psychology*. Novosibirsk, 2022, pp. 187-200.
38. Timokhina, T. V. Tutoring in Preschool Educational Organizations. *Perspectives in Science and Education*, 2018, no. 5(35), pp. 103-109.
39. Tsimbalova, S. Yu., & Mulkamanova, E. V. Tutoring Support of Younger Schoolchildren During Early Optation

in Preparation for the "Young Master" (Babyskills) Championship in the Competence "Teaching in Primary Grades". In: *Pre-Professional Pedagogical Training of Schoolchildren in the System of Continuous Pedagogical Education (From Student to Teacher): Materials of the II International Scientific and Practical Conference*. Yaroslavl, 2023, pp. 227-232.

40. Mayakova, O. S., & Kondratyeva, A. A. Experience of Individual Support of Professional Self-Determination of Adolescents in Tutoring Practice. In: *Innovative Technologies as a Factor of Development: Materials of the International Scientific and Practical Conference within the XXXIV International Specialized Exhibition Agrocomplex-2024*. Ufa, 2024, pp. 306-311.
41. Lipkina, N. G., & Pechkina, O. R. Features of Tutoring Support in the Process of Professional Self-Determination of Senior Students (Using Biology Education as an Example). *Bulletin of Perm State Humanitarian-Pedagogical University. Series No. 1. Psychological and Pedagogical Sciences*, 2020, no. 2, pp. 143-151.
42. Kovaleva, T. M., Kobyscha, E. I., Popova, S. Yu., Terov, A. A., & Cheredilina, M. Yu. Profession "Tutor". Moscow-Tver Publ., 2012. 246 p.

Авторы

Давыденко Валентина Александровна

(Российская Федерация, г. Хабаровск)
Кандидат педагогических наук, доцент,
Руководитель Высшей школы Педагогики и истории;
ФГБОУ ВО «Тихоокеанский государственный университет»
E-mail: 009415@pnu.edu.ru
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5625-5502

Чебровская Светлана Владимировна

(Российская Федерация, г. Хабаровск)
Кандидат психологических наук, доцент,
Доцент Высшей школы Педагогики и истории
ФГБОУ ВО «Тихоокеанский государственный университет»
E-mail: chsv64@rambler.ru
ORCID ID: 0009-0005-4203-7260

Authors

Valentina A. Davydenko

(Russian Federation, Khabarovsk)
Cand. Sci. (Educ.), Associate Professor,
Head of the Graduate School of Pedagogy and History
Pacific National University
E-mail: 009415@pnu.edu.ru
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5625-5502

Svetlana V. Chebrovskaya

(Russian Federation, Khabarovsk)
Cand. Sci. (Psychol.), Associate Professor,
Associate Professor of the Graduate School of Pedagogy and
History
Pacific National University
E-mail: chsv64@rambler.ru
ORCID ID: 0009-0005-4203-7260

Вклад авторов

Давыденко В. А.: администрирование проекта, верификация данных, руководство исследованием

Чебровская С. В.: концептуализация, проведение эмпирического исследования, создание рукописи и ее редактирование

Author's contribution

Valentina A. Davydenko: Project administration, Validation, Supervision

Svetlana V. Chebrovskaya: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - Review & Editing

© Давыденко В. А., Чебровская С. В., 2025

Авторы заявляют об отсутствии конфликта интересов

© Valentina A. Davydenko, Svetlana V. Chebrovskaya, 2025

The author's declared no conflicts of interest